

V. S. Filinova

Personnel management as an integrated system for designing the HR service of an educational organization: a development strategy

KEYWORDS

HR service of an educational organization,
 personnel management,
 integrated system,
 personnel management,
 strategic planning, optimality,
 competence

ABSTRACT

Introduction. The implementation of the main strategic guidelines for the development of the HR service of an educational organization is based on the principles of activity and is carried out using a set of certain actions, methods and technologies that reflect the process of interaction between the HR service personnel and the teaching staff and other employees of the organization. The analysis of scientific literature made it possible to identify as key principles: optimization of human resources, formation of a unique human resources potential, orientation towards the core of human resources. The article presents a set of organizational methods of work, as well as methods and technologies aimed at improving the professional competence of teaching staff when introducing innovative processes by the HR service of an educational organization.

Materials and Methods. In the study, methods of scientific knowledge were used: system analysis, identification and classification, comparison, comparison, generalization of theoretical data. The materials for the study were scientific research in the field of management and education. The authors of the studies we studied are based on recent changes in the world, such as globalization, an increase in the flow of ongoing changes, digital transformation, etc. Noting that these positions generally complement each other, we considered it possible in our study to reflect their relationship in as part of the disclosure of the work of the HR service of an educational organization.

Results and Discussion. The strategy for the development of personnel management is planned in relation to the main activities of the educational organization. To implement the identified areas, management personnel, the HR service and the educational organization need to formulate a set of hierarchically interrelated goals and objectives that reflect the variant features of the educational organization, plan the process of achieving the goals, distributing the main functions of the HR service employees, based on the organizational principles of work and optimally using the entire a range of methods and technologies for the interaction of HR personnel with teaching staff, ensuring the rationality of the innovations introduced, based on the identified professional experience and potential of each employee of the educational organization.

Conclusions. The authors of the article identified the main strategic tracks for the development of the HR service of an educational organization, determined the principles of work, the conditions for the competence readiness of the personnel of the service, management personnel and teachers to introduce innovations. The methods of work and personal characteristics of employees of an educational organization, necessary for optimizing activities, are presented in detail.

Word Cloud Generated by:
<https://wordscound.pythonanywhere.com/>

FOR CITATION

Filinova, V. S. (2023). Personnel management as an integrated system for designing the HR service of an educational organization: a development strategy. *Economic consultant*, (2), 54–72. <https://doi.org/10.46224/ecoc.2023.2.5>

INTRODUCTION

The problem of managing the quality of educational activities of an educational organization in modern conditions is becoming more relevant than ever from the standpoint of the need to ensure the competitiveness of Russian education among the leaders in the field of education.

In our article, we consider an educational organization as an integral system within which the ongoing processes are aimed at the effective achievement of strategic guidelines and development goals. At the same time, it is important to develop a personnel policy, principles and methods of personnel management in the context of ongoing changes in the social and educational spheres, which determines such a direction of work in an educational organization as personnel management.

The process of constructive interaction within the framework of the implementation of strategic goals depends on the degree of interconnectedness of actions, methods and technologies used by the staff of the educational organization, including, among other things, HR service specialists. Designing and implementing successful coordination of the collective interaction of employees of an educational organization will contribute to the implementation of one of the principles of the Federal Law "On Education in the Russian Federation": "creating conditions for the self-realization of each person" [1] and the implementation of the development plan for the project of the National Project "Education" (2019–2024) in terms of "improving the professional skills of managerial personnel" [2].

In our study, it was important to analyze the global experience of personnel management, evaluate the positive aspects, and also identify the possibility of their application in the work of the HR service of an educational organization in modern conditions. The work was based on the following logic: determining the strategic directions for the development of the HR service and the principles of activity that contribute to the implementation of the service development strategy, describing some personal characteristics of an employee of an educational organization, including the HR service as guidelines for professional self-improvement, methods and technologies for effective interaction with the team educational organization in general and each of its employees in particular.

The aim of the study is to study the development strategies of personnel management as an integrated system for designing the HR service of an educational organization.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The study was used general scientific methods: system analysis, identification and classification, comparison, generalization of theoretical data presented in the scientific literature in the field of management and education.

The scientific studies of the authors of the countries of the world (Bulgaria, Indonesia, India, Canada, Pakistan, Russia, USA) were analyzed, reflecting the main trends in the development of education and revealing the role of the HR service of an educational organization, whose work, on the one hand, is subject to the laws of development of personnel management, on the other hand, it is built from the standpoint of using the basic principles of education. It should be noted that the important moments of the work of the HR service and educational organizations that we recorded, described in scientific articles by authors from different countries, largely confirm and complement each other, which made it possible to make a generalized analysis of the changes that have taken place in recent years in the field of management and education. , and present a set of principles, methods and technologies for their use in the strategic activities of the HR service of an educational organization.

LITERATURE REVIEW

The importance of the functioning of the HR service in educational organizations determines the study of the practice of implementing personnel management for designing development strategies.

According to the analyzed sources of scientific literature, we are of the opinion that the concept of "personnel management" is interpreted as "a purposeful activity of the management of an organization, including the development of a personnel policy, principles and methods of personnel management" [3].

By "integrated system for designing the HR service of an educational organization" we mean the preliminary development of the functioning of all structural units of an educational organization, which is based on the interconnection of actions, methods, technologies to achieve project-planned goals.

When analyzing the literature, we drew attention to the work of R. K. Gupta, who notes the complexity of the work of the HR service in modern conditions, when it is necessary to take into account the flow of ongoing changes in one way or another affecting the efficiency of the organization as a whole. And, based on the urgent need, he puts forward several proposals,

among which we have identified those that correspond to the main strategic areas of work of personnel management in an educational organization:

- involving employees in organizational activities and setting goals, including writing a mission and vision;
- empowerment of self-confident, highly qualified employees who can work independently and make decisions;
- ability to work in project teams and in a team with remote experts in own or external project partners;
- change in the development vector from HRM (author from the English "Human Resource Management" – human resource management) to HPM (automatic management of high-potential managers);
- the choice of emphasis on the development of the strengths of the organization" [4].

R. K. Gupta talks about the need to develop employees and the corporate culture of the organization as a whole, we emphasize that this opinion is similar to other authors [5; 6; 7].

To implement the planned, the author Kostromina E. A. notes the importance of improving the personal qualities of the personnel of the HR service as high-potential managers (HPM). We present the personal qualities of employees identified by the author in generalized characteristics, taking into account the specifics of the activities of the HR service in an educational organization:

- the presence of a pronounced ability for professional growth in the learning process and the desire to quickly apply new relevant knowledge in their activities;
- manifestation of the ability to find the right answers to complex professional questions, the possession of a high rate of performance of the assigned work;
- implementation of effective communication based on taking into account the individual characteristics of the colleagues of the educational organization, their readiness to perceive new information in order to achieve the goal;
- the presence of high motivation for success, the desire to master the necessary knowledge, skills and competencies to achieve success;
- manifestation of the ability to implement flexible variable actions depending on the conditions of the situation;
- use in the work of a developed sense of intuition;
- the presence of professional performance in constantly changing conditions of activity [7].

An important feature of work optimization in modern conditions is resistance to crisis influences. Therefore, we believe that the conclusions of E. A. Tanasheva on the principles of anti-crisis management [8] should be taken into account when planning the main development strategies in the personnel management system.

Analyzing the strategic directions of the work of personnel management during the crisis, the author Tanasheva E. A. believes that one of the links in solving the problem of personnel management is the competent choice of the general principles of anti-crisis management:

- optimization of human resources;
- formation of a unique human resources potential;
- focus on the professional core of human resources.

We have identified a group of methods of interaction between the personnel of the HR service of an educational organization with teaching staff and other employees and correlated them with the general principles of anti-crisis management.

So, implementing the principle of optimizing human resources, the work of the HR service of an educational organization can use a set of methods aimed at performing actions that contribute to:

- ensuring a flexible organizational structure of management;
- ensuring a high rate of innovation;
- inspiration of the personnel of the organization when introducing changes in work;
- creating an optimal mode of operation at a sufficiently high level;
- development of rational activity algorithms, description of the conditions for their practical application;
- determination of the optimal mode of operation, taking into account the individual characteristics of the employee;
- development of an effective concept of motivating the personnel of an educational organization through fair remuneration for work;
- the use of socio-psychological aspects of collective activity;
- the use of socio-psychological aspects of collective activity.

Implementing the principle of forming a unique human resources potential, the HR services of an educational organization can use a set of methods aimed at performing actions that contribute to:

- implementation of creative search;
- introduction of a reward system for initiative;
- selection of personnel for work in various professional and environmental conditions;
- specialized training, education and development of personnel.

By implementing the principle of focusing on the core of human resources, the HR services of an educational organization can use a set of methods aimed at performing actions that contribute to:

- ensuring competence-based readiness for successful functioning in a non-standard situation;

- opportunities for career advancement, etc.

Considering that one of the important personal characteristics of employees when working in a non-standard situation is good performance, in our article we present the conclusions of the authors Nastueva E. B., Dottueva T. I., in whose professional activity the mental and physiological causes of a decrease in efficiency were analyzed [10].

The authors Nastuev E. B., Dottuev T. I. identified measures aimed at the formation of endurance in the performance of work:

- creation of an optimal mode of operation at a sufficiently high level;
- development of rational activity algorithms, description of the conditions for their practical application;
- research, accounting and leveling of adverse environmental factors;
- determination of the optimal mode of operation, taking into account the individual characteristics of the employee;
- selection of personnel for work in various professional and environmental conditions based on the data of psychological testing, questionnaires, surveys;
- the correct development of effective systems for assessing and stimulating labor;
- the use of socio-psychological aspects of collective activity;
- development of programs for specialized training, training and development of personnel;
- availability of career growth opportunities [10, p. 216].

The author Gasanova A. A. considers the organizational principles that ensure the effectiveness of the HR service. Consider the principles that can be applied in the work of an educational organization:

- personnel management specialists receive orders directly from the line manager;
- building a "top-down" vertical chain of command;
- achieving the most productive balance between the powers of an employee of the HR service of an educational organization and the work assigned to him;
- development of an effective concept of motivating the personnel of an educational organization through fair remuneration for work [11].

Along with the identified strategies for the development of the HR service of an educational organization, the principles of organizing the work of the service with pedagogical workers, including in crisis conditions, an integrated system of project decisions for personnel management should include the main methods of working with the personnel potential of the organization.

Considering the methods of "self-learning", "developing projects", the author Vukovich G. G. believes that they contribute to the personal development of employees of an educational organization, including HR service personnel, teachers to solve pressing issues.

The application of the "self-learning" method includes:

- understanding the need to expand the range of knowledge and skills in a particular area and overcome the limitations in professional self-training;
- search for answers to specific questions that arise in the course of professional activity;
- manifestation of the desire to train, to do something differently;
- the desire to get a developing effect based on the analysis of one's past experience;
- the study of advanced pedagogical experience as a response to the professional needs of the time.

The application of the "developing projects" method provides for the availability of competencies and knowledge, skills that seem necessary for further development, while the current work does not contain the conditions for their manifestation and development [12].

Analyzing the scientific literature on the success of the educational process, it should be noted that not only the requirements, the desire of the teaching staff determine the success of achieving the goals set for the educational organization, but – first of all – reliance on the patterns revealed by pedagogical science. So, in the 80s of the XX century, on the basis of many years of theoretical and experimental research, starting from the middle of the XX century, the Russian scientist Lerner I. Ya. concluded that the use of the entire set of methods does not ensure the achievement of goals [13]. Knowing the conclusions of Lerner I. Ya. and solving the problem of guaranteed achievement of the results of educational activities, in the 90s of the XX century, the Russian methodologist Turbovsky Ya. S. proposed to use the term "goal-task", the essence of which is that the task planned at each higher level became the goal at the lower level, which must be formulated and an appropriate solution found for it, turning into action [14].

This understanding of the term "goal-task", based on the possibility of moving from one structural level to another to consistently achieve the ultimate goal, can be used by the HR service of an educational organization when planning its work, and with the correct setting of goals and objectives at each of several levels, it is possible to achieve the desired result of the activity.

We note the opinion of N. L. Fetisova that "optimal and effective management of ... units is possible under conditions when the internal functioning of this unit is consistent with the requirements of the task facing it, its technical equipment, the needs and qualifications of personnel, as well as under the conditions of social unity - activity and personal-professional characteristics of a successful leader" [15; 16].

The HR service of an educational organization can proceed from the strategic directions for improving the educational process, when the main directions of the activity of the educational organization are clearly formulated, which we find in the work of Olenev S. M.,

Skvortsov K. V., In Ch., where the main directions for improving the educational work for teenagers – secondary school students:

- formulation of a nationwide passionary idea, “in relation to the characteristics of the typical in the spontaneously developed way of life of the overwhelming majority of social groups of a given age” and the totality of national values and cultural traditions accepted in society, moral norms;
- strengthening aesthetic education at school, the formation of cultural and educational ecosystems of an educational organization, which allow aesthetic education to be carried out comprehensively and informally, outside the context of the disciplines of the artistic cycle ... The formation of aesthetic taste, the development of aesthetic consciousness, should contribute to the development of immunity to base art products, saturated with vulgarity, violence and cynicism;
- propaganda and popularization of psychological support for self-determination, the use of psychological counseling as a norm, and not emergency assistance in a pathological situation” [17, p. 124].

Thus, personnel management provides for the effective activity of the leadership of the HR service of an educational organization, aimed at personnel management – practical activities to provide highly qualified specialists who are able to qualitatively perform the labor functions assigned to them and optimally use the professional creative potential of the staff of the educational organization in their work. At the same time, strategic planning is an important function of management activity, since it is a process of putting forward key areas and programs of activity, provides for the achievement of planned short-term and long-term results based on the relationship of actions, methods and technologies used in the work.

RESULTS

The analysis of scientific literature in the fields of management and education made it possible to identify the main strategies for the development of the HR service of an educational organization:

- interaction between the heads of the HR service and the management personnel of the educational organization in the process of planning and achieving long-term goals set for the educational organization;
- organization of work in project groups, initiative teams (including remotely, using IT technologies and Internet communications, with the involvement of network partners) to solve urgent short-term issues to be resolved in an educational organization;

- supporting the initiative and expanding the capabilities of highly qualified teaching staff and personnel managers to make independent decisions in working with the staff of an educational organization;
- identification of the priority strengths of the educational organization, work on their development;
- improvement of the formative educational environment and corporate culture of the educational organization;
- continuous development of the personnel potential of the educational organization;
- use in the work of the possibilities of modern IT-technologies and Internet communications.

When planning work, the heads of the HR service of an educational organization correlate the activities of the department's employees with the activities of the educational organization, and measure its resources with development needs.

According to the conducted collective research, Yu. P. Zinchenko identifies a number of strategic guidelines for the development of an educational organization in the modern world in the field of education [18].

Universalization, which determined the general approaches to training personnel based on the competence-based approach, when it is possible to choose an individual personal development trajectory, taking into account personal orientation, special inclinations for professional activity.

Of the many existing definitions of the concept of "competence", we adhere to the point of view according to which "competence" is not reduced to the sum of "competencies": of a person, in his interaction with other people in the process of solving various problems" [19].

Knowledge of the structure of competence, which includes professional knowledge, skills; awareness of the value of a particular pedagogical action or set of actions; emotional-volitional regulation and readiness to get involved in the work, "allows you to manage its formation" [19].

Diversification is a principle that "allows diversity, versatility and variability in the development of educational organizations and their management" [20]. It is implemented in the integration of educational programs, the inclusion of flexible learning modules in the curricula, the increase in the scientific and publication activity of teachers in the educational space.

Digitalization of education, the use of various pedagogical models and technologies in the educational process; providing access to new professional information and opportunities to take part in online events of pedagogical communities, "the emergence of new conditions for independent design of the trajectory of self-education and the development of additionally necessary competencies in the optimal period of time, in any place" [21].

Using the opportunity of inclusive education. "... The basis of inclusive education is the concept of overcoming barriers in all trajectories of education of people with disabilities and people with disabilities in order to ensure their full participation in school life" [18].

Organization on the basis of an educational organization of additional education for children as a resource of continuous education throughout life, "defining new forms of non-formal education (quantoriums, circle movement, competitions, grants, educational tracks, etc.)" [18].

To implement the task of developing a modern inclusive educational environment in an educational organization, HR service employees should consider the following:

- availability of the necessary regulatory and legal framework and local acts for the organization of special conditions for the education of students with disabilities [1];
- availability of the necessary material and technical base, vital communications, additional devices, transport, etc.;
- the presence of specialists with basic defectological education who are able to plan and implement an adapted basic general education program, an individual educational route, use special methods and approaches to work in an inclusive education environment;
- it is necessary to provide methodological, methodological, technical, information support for the educational process in terms of inclusion, etc.

Thus, the main task of HR service employees and teachers of an educational organization is the implementation of inclusive education as "a process aimed at specific transformations of the environment and life of people with disabilities and disabilities from an early age to the period of professional self-determination and employment" [18].

Searching for the main characteristics of the activities of the HR service of an educational organization, we noted the relevance of the study by the authors Ulrich D., Brockbank W. [22], who described in their work the key features of the work of this service. Table 1 describes the main functionality of the HR service of an educational organization.

Table 1

Characteristics of the features of the activity HR services
of an educational organization

Features of the activities of the HR service	Description of the actions of the HR service of the educational organization
Emphasis on innovation	Emphasis is placed on seizing opportunities to succeed in the future, as opposed to capitalizing on past successes.
Planned consideration of the opinions of teachers and employees	Short and quick Internet surveys are a good tool for drawing generalized conclusions about intermediate results achieved. Identification of opinions about teamwork, including the work of the HR service

Using Internet Chats	Modern managers have the opportunity to conduct a dialogue with colleagues through modern means of communication at a convenient time for everyone
Optimization of the current process	The HR service can create effective bottom-up communication channels, analyze the requests of teachers and staff and provide them with an effective response
Offer collection system	This system meets the principle of “continuous improvement”, and this is ensured by the high activity of colleagues who make their suggestions, as well as the willingness of managers to take these suggestions into account when working.
Systematic support of administrative systems (timely documentation, compliance with procedures for hiring and transferring employees, payment of compensation and benefits, etc.)	Maintaining administrative systems at the proper level requires the following conditions: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • personal approach to each employee; • quick response from the administrative system; • ease of use of registration of work procedures (for example, applications can be submitted using the necessary forms in electronic form; all changes in the employee's work status can be automatically broadcast through the corporate information system); • accurate and correct execution. The accuracy of execution instills confidence in the system and increases the credibility of the HR service. On the contrary, even a small mistake can cause a big problem
Availability of individual abilities of HR specialists and their development	The process of developing individual abilities involves: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • coaching (helping employees turn their ideas into action); • management (development of an action plan to ensure the proper level of development of the individual abilities of employees necessary for the organization); • personal work with each employee (clarification of the company's strategic priorities and development of skills that contribute to the achievement of individual goals and ambitions)
Talent support and development	The competitive advantage of any organization is capable employees who, on the one hand, are competent and qualified to do their job (that is, they can do it), and on the other hand, are committed to the interests of the organization (that is, they want to do their job). Regular assessment of the compliance of abilities and requirements will always help to determine the set of skills required for work, as well as competence deficits

The characteristics presented in Table 1 can be considered from the standpoint of the methods of interaction between the personnel of the HR service of an educational organization and its employees.

Taking into account the key guidelines for the development of an educational organization in the modern world (universalization of the training of teaching staff based on a competency-based approach, variability in the development of educational organizations, digitalization,

etc.) in the development of strategies for the development of the HR service of an educational organization allows you to build the effective activities of its management and each employee to solve actual problems of education.

DISCUSSION

When designing a personnel policy in an educational organization, the leadership of the HR service puts forward as one of the key tasks the provision of professional interaction between participants in educational relations, which has a certain influence on them, based on knowledge and use of the laws of pedagogy, special methods and technologies.

According to Land S., the basis of mentoring for successful work aimed at improving the professional practical competencies of a mentee (having less experience), a mentor (having more experience) needs to provide several conditions:

- active perception of information and following the advice of a mentor;
- planning the mentee development trajectory based on either identified requests or diagnostic data;
- promotion of personality-developing mental goals;
- the use of personality-developing mental feedback.

At the same time, the mentor himself must have the competence to “inspire and set tasks that challenge abilities” [23].

The use of such well-known technologies as mentoring, coaching, tutoring in the experience of mentoring involves putting forward a certain system of questions aimed at diagnosing the formed readiness of teaching staff and HR service employees to perform assigned tasks (mentoring), identifying potential resources of the individual to achieve the planned long-term results (coaching), for mastering new competencies (tutoring). For the professional growth of employees of an educational organization, it is important to self-propose questions that professional reality poses, without answering which it is impossible to achieve the desired results.

Let us note the peculiarity of the work of the HR service in an educational organization, such as the appropriate use of the potential of the team. In Russian pedagogy, the experience of Makarenko A.S., which is used in practice, is widely known, as was discussed at the All-Russian webinar (2017), dedicated to his work: “If we talk about the educational environment formed by the efforts of Anton Semenovich, then it was “... a single a collective in which all educational processes are organized, and an individual member of this collective feels his dependence on him - on the collective, he is devoted to the interests of the collective,

defends these interests and ... cherishes these interests" [24, p. 244]. From the analysis of foreign experience on the possibility of collective potential, we note the point of view of Fullan M.: "Thanks to the collective potential of the group – the educational systems of schools, districts, states – are being improved. High collective potential, and collective potential in general, which ultimately means something, is when the group improves together. The level of emotional involvement and professional competence, which is achieved by the realization of the collective potential, is immeasurably higher than that which can be achieved by the realization of the individual potential" [25].

Given the rapidly occurring changes in the modern world, it is impossible not to touch on the use of IT technologies as an opportunity to optimize management decisions. The author Anguelov K. revealed the main and extended functions in the work of personnel management from the position of using digital technologies [26].

Table 2, based on the data of work [26], provides examples of the functionality of personnel management and outlines their advantages.

Table 2

Application of IT-technologies in the functionality of personnel management

Title of function	Advantages
Main functions	
Digitization of classical business processes related to human resource management	Recruiting, time management, payroll, career growth, motivation, training, social environment
Integration of information into the organization	Fast and efficient implementation of business processes involving several departments of the organization
Integrating organizational information with external databases	Communication with various state or local authorities (according to the laws of the country)
Search and processing of large data arrays	Quickly find the necessary information and present it in the form of a report and / or any official document
Integration with other, depending on the specifics of the organization, information systems (relationship management systems, integrated resource planning, etc.).	Information received from human resource management is available for use, processing and analysis by all interested management personnel
Advanced features	
Analysis of large datasets	Statistical data processing allows you to obtain the necessary information, ensure the implementation of human resource management processes at a qualitatively new level
Predictions based on big data analysis	The function is associated with the use of elements of artificial intelligence, such as hidden facts or trends related to various aspects of human resource management, such as seasonal/climatic trends in the team (sick leave, vacations, leaving work, etc.); the level of remuneration that serves as a motivator for employees of the organization; forecasts of projected tasks fulfillment in certain calendar periods/stages and much more

Virtual communication with employees	Simplified communication between employees and the HR department is one of the features of HRIS, which not only saves man-hours, but also demonstrates the assessment of an employee's personal time in his communication with the administration
Creation of new management processes aimed at improving the professionalism of the organization's employees	The use of artificial intelligence, data analysis, the ability to make forecasts and virtual communication with employees create the prerequisites for creating new management processes that are ineffective without HRIS. An example would be to book a specific day and time for a shared workplace or conference room (in the case of such an open space policy in the enterprise) through a digital application included with HRIS
Integration of artificial intelligence in organizations	The function implies not only forecasting associated with the analysis of large data sets, but also a general integrated approach to managing an organization using artificial intelligence, typical of Enterprise 5.0: salary motivation, artificial intelligence guidance in work, assistance in evaluation and selection, early identification of talents. The main specificity is to use the most complete, effective and creative possibilities of artificial intelligence in the overall management of the organization

From the data in Table 2 it can be seen that the modern capabilities of IT technologies and Internet services can be of great help in the work of the HR service of an educational organization.

Along with improving the process of managing an educational organization, the widespread use of advanced information and communication technologies, its management and management personnel of the HR service are introducing various methods to improve the professionalism of teaching staff, on which the quality of education of the younger generation depends.

As an example, let us cite the experience of the authors Wahyudin Noor, Juhji Juhji, who, while solving the problem of improving the quality of education, believe that it would be rational for a number of Islamic educational institutions to create a common professionally managed center of excellence, the functioning of which met the primary task of hiring trained teaching staff. with high personal moral qualities. The authors are convinced that the level of training of students directly depends on improving the efficiency of managing the work of the HR service of educational organizations, in particular, the organizational activities of this service and personnel management. In [27, p. 7383] talks about the advantages of the madrasah in the process of recruiting the necessary teaching staff: providing an independent assessment of the level of competence and professional suitability of accepted teachers, determining their level of training,

conducting the recruitment procedure, signing contracts, etc. The work of the HR service includes: bringing the requirements to the entire team and provisions necessary to achieve a particular position; organization of vocational training, development of talent and creativity; application of motivation methods. The existence of guarantees and certainty regarding a future career, the authors consider a necessary source of enthusiasm shown in the work of each employee. The authors rightly note that not only financial satisfaction is a determining factor of work, but also “the existing work environment and work culture contributed to the satisfaction of employees of MAN Yogyakarta III” [27, p. 7389]. The conclusion reached by the authors of the article corresponds to the modern understanding of solving the problems of education – the implementation of the functions of managing the employees of an educational organization is directly related to the forms of satisfying requests – it is important to increase physical and psychological development, continue professional development, and constantly develop “skills, talents and creative abilities; the atmosphere and culture of work created by the madrasah must be made sufficient for the satisfaction and convenience of a person” [27, p. 7390].

In the course of discussions, we would like to note the fact of the similarity of the positions of researchers from different countries of the world in an effort to generalize the best pedagogical experience and give it development. Above, we cited the opinion of authors from Indonesia, and we note that in Soviet and Russian pedagogy this strategic task was implemented in the 90s of the XX century as part of the methodology for diagnosing mass pedagogical experience, when “a unified information system was created across the country, allowing comprehensively, systematically and targetedly take into account the needs of not only each teaching staff, but also each teacher, purposefully using the achievements of science, and advanced and innovative experience” [28, p. 8], part of this experience is reflected in the framework of the modern project "Mutual learning of cities" (organizer – Moscow).

Thus, as a result of the analysis of literature and discussion of scientific works of authors from various countries devoted to the topic of our study, it is noted that the essence of the principles of personnel management of the HR service of an educational organization is skillful system design and the use of various methods that contribute to the development of productive interaction of all employees of the organization, aimed at achieving the set goals.

CONCLUSION

In the course of our study, based on the study of scientific research in the field of personnel management and in the field of education, the following were identified:

- the main strategic directions for the development of the HR service of an educational organization;
- the basic principles of interaction between the personnel of the HR service of an educational organization with teaching staff and employees of the organization in modern conditions;
- personal qualities of employees of an educational organization (including the HR service) as guidelines for self-improvement;
- methods of overcoming the resistance of employees to innovations used in the work of the HR service of an educational organization;
- methods and technologies for effective interaction of employees of the HR service of an educational organization with each other and with teaching staff and other employees of the organization;
- the conclusions of two fundamental studies in the field of education are given, one of which speaks of the insufficiency of applying a system of methods and technologies to achieve the intended goals [13] facing an educational organization, the other presents a generalized algorithm for achieving strategic long-term goals / development strategies [14], which in the practice of improving the work of personnel management can be applied both in the design of the work of the HR service, and in the design of the main activities of an educational organization.

It has been established that not only financial remuneration is the determining factor for successful work [29; 30], but also a formed creative working environment [31; 32], in which professional relations are built on the basis of the recognition of the basic rules of pedagogical culture, collective interaction and mutual support, contributes to the satisfaction of the needs of the employees of the educational organization.

Thus, personnel management is a complex integrated system that reflects the development of personnel policy, principles of activity and actions used, methods and technologies for the effective management of an educational organization.

REFERENCES

1. Federal Law "On Education in the Russian Federation" (as amended) No. 273-FZ of December 29, 2012. Available at: <https://zakonobobrazovani.ru/glava-1/statya-3> (accessed: 05/14/2023).
2. National project "Education", 2019–2024. Available at: <https://edu.gov.ru/nationalproject/plan/> (accessed: 05/14/2023).

3. Personnel management. Available at: <http://www.upravlenie24.ru/kadrmanagment.htm> (accessed: 05/14/2023).
4. Gupta, R. K. (2022). HR management and staff development. Available at: https://www.researchgate.net/publication/362929183_hr_management_and_staff_development (accessed: 14.05.2023).
5. Kalyuzhnov, N. V. (2007). Corporate culture as a factor in increasing the competitiveness of an organization: Diss. Cand. Sociol. Sci., Irkutsk, 187.
6. Hanif, H. M., Ramsha, F., & Shaheryar, S. (2020). Corporate culture and values: a case of starbuck's corporate culture. Available at: https://www.researchgate.net/publication/343110602_corporate_culture_and_values_a_case_of_starbuck's_corporate_culture (accessed: 14.05.2023).
7. Kostromina, E. A. (2018). The specifics of managing high-potential managers (HPM) in a modern organization. *Bulletin of the Moscow University named after S. Yu. Witte. Series 1: Economics and Management*, 2 (25). Available at: <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/spetsifika-upravleniya-vysokopotentzialnymi-managerami-hpm-v-sovremennoy-organizatsii> (accessed: 02/14/2023).
8. Tanasheva, E. A. (2019). Anti-crisis management of the organization's personnel. *Young Scientists Forum*, 1–3 (29), 545–554.
9. Babansky, Yu. K. (1977). Optimization of the learning process (General didactic aspect). Moscow, Pedagogy Publ., 256.
10. Nastuev, E. B., & Dottuev, T. I. (2020). Personnel management in an educational organization while ensuring the quality of education. *Education. The science. Scientific personnel*, 3. Available at: <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/kadrovyi-management-v-obrazovatelnoy-organizatsii-pri-obespechenii-kachestva-obrazovaniya> (accessed: 02/14/2023).
11. Gasanova, A. A. (2019). Personnel management in the organization management system. *Innovation Science*, 11, 50–53.
12. Vukovich, G. G. (2019). Personnel management: theory and methodology. *Economy. Profession. Business*, 4, 20–25.
13. Lerner, I. Ya. (1981). Didactic foundations of teaching methods. Moscow, Pedagogy Publ., 186.
14. Turbovskoy, Ya. S., & Provotorov, V. N. (1995). Diagnostic bases of goal-setting in education. Moscow, ITOiP RAO Publ., 117.
15. Fetisova, N. L. (2003). Personal and activity characteristics of an effective leader of a scientific unit: Sociological and managerial analysis: Diss. Cand. Sociol. Sci., Moscow, 197.
16. Fetisova, N. L. (2022). HR service of a modern educational organization in the context

- of global digitalization: development strategy. *Economic consultant*, 38 (2), 30–42. DOI: 10.46224/ecoc.2022.2.3.
17. Olenev, S. M., Skvortsov, K. V., & In, Ch. (2020). Modern tasks of educating adolescents and youth in the socio-cultural context. *Pedagogical Journal of Bashkortostan*, 4–5 (89–90), 116–126. DOI: 10.21510/1817-3292-2020-89-90-4-5-116-126.
 18. Pedagogical education in modern Russia: strategic guidelines for development: monograph. South Federal University; scientific editor Yu. P. Zinchenko. Rostov-on-Don-Taganrog, Southern Federal University, 2020. 612 p. Available at: https://elibrary.ru/download/elibrary_44329467_54374825.pdf (accessed: 05/14/2023).
 19. Zimnyaya, I. A. Competence and competence in the context of the competency-based approach in education. Available at: http://rusreadorg.ru/ckeditor_assets/attachments/63/i_a_zymnaya_competency_and_competence.pdf (accessed: 05/14/2023).
 20. Pedagogical encyclopedia. Available at: <https://didacts.ru/termin/diversifikacija-sistemy-obrazovanija.html> (accessed: 05/14/2023).
 21. Bermus, A. G., Bondarev, M. G., Kirik, V. A., Kulikovskaya, I. E., & Chumicheva, R. M. (2020). The Concept of Development of Pedagogical Education in a Federal Multidisciplinary University (on the Example of SFU). Pedagogical education in modern Russia: strategic guidelines for development: monograph. Rostov-on-Don-Taganrog, Southern Federal University, 516–518. Available at: https://elibrary.ru/download/elibrary_44329467_54374825.pdf (accessed: 05/14/2023).
 22. Ulrich, D., & Brockbank, W. (2010). HR in the fight for competitive advantage. Tr. from English. Moscow, Pretext Publ., 362.
 23. Landa, S. What is mentoring and how does it work. Available at: <https://slacademy.ru/blogmentoring> (accessed: 05/14/2023).
 24. Kosenko, T. S., Ligostaeyev, A. G., Nalivaiko, N. V., & Yakovleva, I. V. (2017). Transcript of the webinar «Do the general school and domestic education need Makarenko in modern conditions?». *Philosophy of Education*, 73, 4, 232–249. Available at: <https://sibran.ru/upload/iblock/3c5/3c51580c033f02132ec2c58461cacb81.pdf> (accessed: 14.05.2023).
 25. Fullan, M. (2010). All Systems Go: The Change Imperative for Whole System Reform. Thousand Oaks, CA: Corwin. DOI: 10.4135/9781452219554.
 26. Anguelov, K. (2022). ICT as the New Age of Development of HR Management.
 27. Noor, W., & Juhji, J. (2022) Implementation of HR management functions: A quality-analysis. *Al-Ishlah: Jurnal Pendidikan*, 14, 4, 7381–7392. DOI: 10.35445/alishlah.v14i4.2311.
 28. Turbovskoy, Ya. S. (2012). Interaction of pedagogical science and the system of

domestic education as a controlled process: monograph. Moscow, FGNU ITIP RAO, publishing center IET, 276.

29. Diachkova, A. V., Sandler, D. G., & Avramenko, E. S. (2020). Case of using simulation in education for business analysts. *Economic Consultant*, 3 (31), 104–114.
30. Diachkova, A. V., & Kulkova, L. I. (2019). Financing an educational institution: the search for an optimal business model. *Modern problems of science and education*, 2, 85–93.
31. Tomyuk, O. N. (2013). Creativity: ontological aspect. *Epistemes: a collection of scientific articles*. Issue. 8: Problems of modern ontology. Ekaterinburg, Azhur Publ., 82–90.
32. Tomyuk, O. N. (2014). Creativity and Lawmaking: Ontological Aspect. *Journal of Siberian Federal University. Humanities and Social Sciences*, 7, 8, 1293–1300.

INFORMATION ABOUT THE AUTHOR

Vera S. Filinova (Russia, Moscow) – Cand. Sci. (Pedagogy), Expert of Research and Monitoring Department. Corporate University of Moscow Education. E-mail: filinovavs@corp-univer.ru. ORCID ID: 0000-0003-1433-9374.

Available: <https://statecounsellor.wordpress.com/2023/06/01/filinova-2/>

Received: Dec 16, 2022 | **Accepted:** Feb 12, 2023 | **Published:** Jun 1, 2023

Editor: Norlaile S. Hudin, PhD (Management). Universiti Pendidikan Sultan Idris, MALAYSIA

Copyright: © 2023 Filinova, V. This is an open access article distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License, which permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided the original author and source are credited.

Competing interests: The authors have declared that no competing interests exist.